

Magnetism, Lorentz Invariance and Addition of a Dimension Part II

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Maxwell's electromagnetic equations, which are based on experimental observations for electric E and magnetic fields B , lead mathematically to the relationships: $B = \text{grad} \times A$ and $E = -\text{grad} \phi - d/dt A$ partial ((1))

We argued in Part I that one may consider two static charges q_2 and q_1 . The first charge has a potential energy $q_2 \phi(r)$ where ϕ is the electrostatic potential created by the other charge. We argued that given that rest mass m_0 transforms into (pc, E) under a Lorentz transformation, then $(0, q_2 \phi)$ should transform into $(\text{vector } q_2 A, q_2 \text{ new } \phi)$. We further argued that if one creates a classical action $L dt$ using the sum of the two Lorentz invariants: $-dt E + dx p - dt q_2 \phi + q_2 A dx$ or: $dt(-E + p \cdot v - q_2 \phi + q_2 v \cdot A)$, one may obtain the Lagrange equation of motion. We argued that if one assumes a retarded time $t - R/c$, where c is the speed of light, one may obtain the results ((1)). In this latter case, one does not use the full Maxwell electromagnetic equations, only the idea that $q_2 \phi$ is energy. In this note, we try to argue that one may extend this scenario and try to predict that the photon is represented by an energy density of $.5c^2 E \cdot E + .5c^2 B \cdot B$ with a momentum density of $c^2 E \times B$. Given that the speed of light c appears in the Lorentz invariant approach and not explicitly in Maxwell's equations, it seems that c (speed of light in a vacuum), must be a function of some electromagnetic parameters in Maxwell's equations.

Maxwell's Equations

Maxwell's equations are given in (1) as:

$$\text{Grad} \cdot E = \text{charge density}/ \epsilon_0 \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{grad} \cdot B = 0 \quad ((2b))$$

$$\text{Grad} \times E = -dB/dt \text{ partial} \quad ((2c)) \quad \text{grad} \times B = \mu_0 (J + \epsilon_0 dE/dt \text{ partial}) \quad ((2d))$$

Here ϵ_0 and μ_0 are electromagnetic constants.

Given ((2a)), one may immediately write: $B = \text{grad} \times A$ ((3)), where A is some vector field.

Given ((2c)), if one takes d/dt partial of ((3)) then $dB/dt \text{ partial} = -\text{grad} \times dA/dt \text{ partial}$ so it follows that:

$$E = -dA/dt \text{ partial} - \text{grad} \phi \quad ((4))$$

where ϕ is some scalar function and the minus sign is used for convenience

In particular, the forms ((1)) follow directly from two of Maxwell's equations ((2a)) and ((2c)).

Furthermore, one may use Maxwell's equations to create the well-known form:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + 1/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) + c^3 \text{grad} \cdot (\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}) = \text{terms with sources} \quad ((5))$$

In the case that one sets the sources to 0 (i.e. charge density and \mathbf{J} current density), one may write wave equations separately for \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} , which shows they are treated mathematically in the same way, even though some constants may differ.

Maxwell argued that the source-free cases above describe a photon (due to a speed calculation which matched the speed of light in a vacuum).

Lorentz Invariants

In Part I, we suggested that one may obtain ((1)) without knowing about Maxwell's electromagnetic equations except for the fact that a charged particle is associated with a function ϕ such that $q\phi$ represent electrostatic energy of a second charge q and the important assumption about retarded time, which often appears in electromagnetic texts (2) i.e.

If a measurement is made at (\mathbf{r} vector) at time t , with \mathbf{r} vector being measured from a fixed origin and a source charge is at (\mathbf{r}' vector) (measured from the same origin), then one uses charge density:

$$\text{Charge density} (\mathbf{r}' \text{ vector}, t - R/c) \quad \text{where } R = | \mathbf{r} \text{ vector} - \mathbf{r}' \text{ vector} | \text{ and } c = \text{the speed of light in a vacuum.} \quad ((6))$$

Retarded time is associated with important assumptions.

- A. First, it suggests that a photon (which at first might seem to have nothing to do with electromagnetic theory) carries electromagnetic signals.
- B. Secondly, c is the same in all frames of references.. One does not use different c values for each speed of a moving source charge, for example. (This is the same assumption made by Einstein in his treatment of Special Relativity.)

The use of retarded time, i.e. the presence of photon signals seems to be a strong assumption. At first glance, one would think that the speed of light would have nothing to do with electric and magnetic fields. We note, however, that if one considers a particle with a rest mass m_0 and no charge, $(0, m_0)$ and transforms it, then the transformation matrix must have v/b appear to be dimensionless. " b " is a constant which makes v dimensionless, but the same constant seems to be used for any frame (i.e. any v). It is not at all clear what this constant should be. We argued in previous notes that there exists a photon, which does not seem to have rest mass, but still has energy and momentum (strikes a target). If one applies the ideas of $E^2 + p^2 b^2 = m_0^2 c^4$ to the case of $m_0=0$, the $E=pb$, but this is consistent with $b=c$. Thus, the notion of photon enters into special relativity even if no notion of electromagnetism is present. For example, Einstein used photons to measurements in his special relativity arguments.

We suggest that the notion of the photon should still be present in the electromagnetic case, but this time electromagnetic signals seem to be sent from various charge points to a measurement point. If the signals are represented by photons, then there is retarded time. Otherwise, there would have to be infinitely rapid signals. { In principle, one could perform two calculations, one with instantaneous signals and the other with retarded time and the latter would match experiment.)

It was shown explicitly in Part I, one may create the classical action from the sum of two Lorentz invariants:

$$L dt = -Edt + p dx - q \phi dt + q A dx \rightarrow L dt = dt (-E + p \cdot v - q \phi + q v \cdot A) \quad ((7))$$

One may then write the Lagrangian equation: $d/dt dL/dv_i - dL/dx_i = 0 \quad ((8))$

keeping in mind that t in A and ϕ are replaced with retarded time $t - R/c \quad ((6))$.

This leads to the form $((1))$ as shown explicitly in Part I.

Is It Possible to Extend the Ideas from the Lorentz Invariants?

By using the sum of the two Lorentz invariants $((7))$ and the idea that the resulting L is stationary, one may calculate the equation of motion and deduce that there is a force $qvxB$ where $B = \text{grad} \times A$ and a force qE where $E = -\text{grad} \phi - dA/dt \text{ partial} \quad ((1))$. These ideas follow from special relativity, the notion of $q \phi$ being electrostatic energy and the use of retarded time. This result is compatible with Maxwell's equations. In fact, the results $((1))$ immediately yield two of Maxwell's equations (as well as the Lorentz force law):

$$F=qE+qvxB \text{ (Lorentz) } , \text{ grad dot } B =0 \text{ and } dB/dt \text{ partial} = - \text{grad} \times E \quad ((9))$$

The other two Maxwell equations, however, do not follow.

We ask: Is it possible to deduce any more from this line of reasoning?

First, we write the general result using: $-\text{grad} \times E = dB/dt \text{ partial}$. Then:

$$.5 d/dt \text{ partial } B \cdot B = -\text{grad} \cdot (ExB) \quad ((10))$$

$$\{ B_i e_{ijk} d_j E_k = - d_j e_{jik} B_i E_k = d_j e_{jki} E_k B_i \}$$

We suggest that the use of frame invariance constant speed of c in the retarded time suggests that c (associated with a photon), must be directly connected to electromagnetism. If c is the same in all frames, there should be no preferred frame, i.e. no rest frame. We note that we

originally started with a $q\phi$ in a rest frame, but in order to describe a photon, there is no longer a charge source. One simply tries to apply equations linked with E and B.

The removal of the bias towards E (which existed in the rest frame) suggests, we speculate, that E and B should satisfy similar math equations (with the exceptions of perhaps some constants).

$\frac{1}{2} B \cdot B$ already has the same math structure as $\frac{1}{2} E \cdot E$ which is the self-electrostatic energy in a rest frame. Due to symmetry of equations, one would suggest another two equations: $\text{grad} \cdot E = 0$ and $\text{grad} \times B = dE/dt$ partial for no sources.

Then $\frac{1}{2} E \cdot E$ has the appearance of electric self energy and $\frac{1}{2} B \cdot B$, magnetic self-energy. Given this symmetry, it follows that ((10)) :

$$C_1 \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} E \cdot E = - \text{grad} \cdot (E \times B) \quad ((11))$$

We introduce c_1 as an extra constant. In such a case, for a lack of sources (charge and current density) one has:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} \{ C_1 \frac{1}{2} E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2} C_2 B \cdot B \} + c_3 \text{grad} \cdot (E \times B) = 0 \quad ((12)) \text{ for a photon}$$

((12)) may be compared with the equation resulting from Maxwell's equations namely (2):

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} \{ \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{\mu_0} B \cdot B \} + \frac{1}{\mu_0} E \times B = 0 \quad ((13))$$

For a photon in Maxwell's theory: $|E| = |B| c$, so the factor coefficient of B dot B is:

$$\epsilon_0 / (\epsilon_0 \mu_0) \quad \text{suggesting that } c = 1/(\epsilon_0 \mu_0) \text{ as argued above } ((14)).$$

We note that ((12)) is more than an energy momentum balance type of equation because we have shown in a previous note that if one linearizes ((12)) by factoring out $(E + i B)$, then one obtains a quantum wave-equation for a photon with ϵ_{ijk} , the Levi-Civita symbol representing the spin-1 matrix.

Guessing the Form of Two More Maxwell's Equations

Given that $\text{grad} \cdot B = 0$ and $-\text{grad} \times E = dB/dt$ partial lead to ((11)), and the symmetry between B and E for the photon case, we suggest that two more equations which should hold are:

$$\text{Grad} \cdot E = \text{source function 1} \quad ((15a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{grad} \times B = dE/dt \text{ partial} + \text{source function 2} \quad ((15b))$$

Dropping the source function yields symmetry between E and B up to constant coefficients.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that given the idea that a source charge creates an electrostatic field ϕ in a rest frame which creates an energy $q\phi$ for a charge q at some point, one may use a Lorentz transformation to suggest that $(0, q\phi)$ transforms into $(qA, q\phi')$. In order to find A and ϕ , one may obtain a Lagrangian from the action given as the sum of two Lorentz invariants $-Edt + pdx - q\phi dt + qA dx \rightarrow = dt \{ -E + p \cdot v - q\phi + qv \cdot A \}$. If one applies the Lorentz equation $d/dt \partial L/\partial v_i - \partial L/\partial x_i = 0$ and uses $t - |R|/c$, i.e. retarded time, then one obtains two force pieces: qE and $qv \times B$ such that $E = -\text{grad } \phi' - dA/dt$ and $B = \text{grad } \times A$. This immediately leads to two of Maxwell's em equations: $\text{Grad } \cdot B = 0$ and $-\text{grad } \times E = dB/dt$.

These two may be combined to obtain: $\frac{1}{2} d/dt \partial B \cdot B = \text{grad } \cdot (E \times B)$ ((C))

The use of retarded time with a constant c (for any frame of reference) suggests that (A) the photon is related to E and B and (B) that the photon has no rest frame so E and B should be on the same mathematical footing.

We suggest that if $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$ is the self-energy in a rest frame of a charge, then $\epsilon_0 c c B \cdot B$ and $\epsilon_0 E \cdot E$ should be the self magnetic and electric energies in the moving frame. We suggest from ((C)) and no rest frame that one should have symmetry (up to constant coefficients) and so suggest that:

$$d/dt \partial (\frac{1}{2} (\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + c c \epsilon_0 B \cdot B) + \text{constant } \text{grad } \cdot E \times B = 0$$

which is normally a result taken from Maxwell's equations. Linearizing this yields a quantum equation for the photon (if $E \rightarrow i d/dt$ and $p \rightarrow -\text{grad}$) with e_{ijk} being the spin matrix.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maxwell%27s_equations
2. Reitz, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory (Addison Wesley: 1980)